

Effects of Low Frequency Vibration on OAEs

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Abstract. Transient Evoked Otoacoustic Emissions (TEOAEs) discovered by Kemp (2002), are sounds of cochlear origin, evoked by click stimuli and recorded by means of a probe microphone fitted into the ear canal and are sensitive to the function of the outer hair cells (OHCs). It is widely accepted that electromotile properties make the OHCs an active bio-amplifier located within the cochlea. The main purpose of the current study was to assess the combined synergistic effect of exposure to noise and hand-arm vibration on TEOAEs. A custom-made wooden box made to house a Craftsman Drill generated noise and vibration exposures required for the current study. A total of twenty participants (13 males and 7 females) participated and experienced (mean Leq = 82 dBA) and vibration measured with accelerometer sensors on head (mean vibration exposure = 0.08 /sec²). TEOAEs evoked by clicks were captured utilizing the Scout Sport Bio-logic System. For each participant, OAEs were measured in baseline and post-exposure (noise only versus Noise+HAV) conditions. After statistically controlling for Body Mass Index, hearing sensitivity and ear canal volume differences across participants, results showed that noise+HAV exposure generated a significant change in OAEs in female participants, even after adjusting for differences in ear canal volume across males and females.

INTRODUCTION

Current models support important role of Outer Hair Cells (OHCs) within the cochlea as bioamplifiers and feed energy back to the Inner Hair Cells (IHCs). This mechano-electrical energy generated by OHCs is used for cochlear transduction by IHCs before auditory nerve fibers can relay action potentials to the brain [1]. These OHCs are widely considered the first line of defense, and take the brunt of the initial damage from occupational noise or ototoxic agents before IHCs get affected [2]. Otoacoustic emissions (OAEs) are sounds that are produced in the cochlea and evoked by brief click or tonal stimuli [3]. Otoacoustic Emissions provide quick, efficient and non-invasive measures of healthy outer hair cell functioning in humans [4]. Humans exposed to loud noise are expected to have weaker/absent OAE while, ears having minimal noise exposure have higher-amplitude OAEs.

The mechano-electrical force needed for cochlear transduction is attributed to electromotility associated with the lateral wall of the OHCs [5]. Based on the piezoelectric model by Ramamoorthy, Deo, & Grosh [1], the outer hair cells (OHCs) provides both: a) forward transduction of energy (mechanical deflection of OHCs stereocilia to electrical energy in the form of action potential) and b) a reverse transduction (electrical currents from OHCs feeding mechanical energy to the inner hair cells - IHCs). These properties make the OHCs function as an active bio-amplifier located within the cochlea. When loud noise exposures or other occupational hazards diminish OHCs function, this amplifier action is lost resulting in irreversible Sensorineural Hearing Loss (SNHL).

There are two types of OAEs used clinically. Transient evoked otoacoustic emissions (TEOAE) involve presentation of broad band clicks (1000Hz – 2000 Hz) to the ear canal and recording of the OAE response in the time and frequency domain [4]. The second type of OAEs are distortion product OAEs (DPOAEs) involve presentation of two primary tones of frequencies f1 and f2 to the ear canal and recording of the distortion product (2f1-f2) and published work by Sisto et al. [2] showed synergistic effects of noise and HAV on objective measures of auditory function (Distortion Product Otoacoustic Emissions-DPOAEs). The combined effects of noise and HAV on DPOAEs were much stronger than noise only and HAV only conditions [2].

The exact mechanism underlying generation of OAEs are under debate at this time, but evidence supports changes in OAEs associated with occupational or recreational noise exposure. Absent or reduced amplitude OAEs can be an early warning for noise induced hearing loss. These findings were supported in a longitudinal study conducted by Miller et al. [6]. They studied two groups of participants, one exposed to loud noise exposures in the workplace and the other group (quiet) with minimal noise exposure. Results showed that the group with greater noise exposure had decrease in OAE amplitude over time in the higher frequencies. In contrast, for the group working in a quiet environment did not have significant changes in OAEs over time. Miller et al. [7] tested OAEs and audio threshold in 338 navy sailors in aircraft carrier. OAEs were tested before and six months after deployment on the aircraft carrier. Results suggested a significant decrease in OAE at post deployment for OAEs at 4kHz. This indicated that OAEs are sensitive to occupational noise exposure and such individuals must be placed in hearing conservation program. Similar changes in OAEs were reported in another study in military soldiers exposed to small military firearms over a 2 year period by Duvdevany and Furst [8]. Audiometric thresholds significantly increased following 2 years of deployment and the biggest change in TEOAEs in this longitudinal study was seen at end of the 24th month testing (relative to 1, 3, 6, and 18 months). This makes it critical to include the individuals with reduced OAEs in the hearing conservation program. Another recreational hearing loss study on band musicians by Krishnamurti et al. [9] found weakened OAEs in student band musicians and band directors who experienced music overexposure (when compared with non- band students).

Very few controlled studies have addressed interaction between noise and vibration in humans. Vibration exposure may increase hearing loss in workers exposed to noisy jobs coupled with vibration and often comes in two forms: 1) Whole Body Vibration (WBV) – vibration transmitted via the supporting surface (feet/buttocks/reclining position) in vibrating surfaces or 2) Hand arm vibration (HAV)– hands in direct contact with handles, paddles, flat surface of vibrating equipment/tools. Manninen [10] studied men who were exposed to loud noise and WBV. The researcher studied 2 levels of noise (85 dB and 98 dB) with two frequencies of vibration exposure (5 Hz and 10 Hz). The 3 exposure conditions were noise only, noise+5Hz and noise+10Hz. For noise only conditions (exposures of 85 dB and 98 dB), the mean threshold shift at 4000 Hz was 12 dB for 85 dB and 28 dB for 98 dB. When 5 Hz vibration was added, temporary threshold shift increased by 3 dB for 85 dB noise exposure and 7 dB for 98 dB noise level. Similarly, temporary threshold increased by 2 dB for 85 dB exposure and 4 dB for 98dB exposure. The lower frequency (5Hz) when added to noise exposure, resulted in greater temporary threshold than 10Hz. The authors attributed the differential effects of vibration to a resonance effect (vibration dose and individual body’s vibration at the same level). Sisto et al. [2] used 3 exposure conditions for a duration of 3 minutes each followed by a rest period of 4 minutes: HAV only, noise only, and Noise+HAV. The subjects were exposed to a HAV dose of 30 m/sec² at 60Hz and using 20% of the Maximum Voluntary Contraction (MVC) by gripping the handle connected to a shaker. The noise dose exposure was white noise at 94 dBA. DPOAEs were measured before and after each of the exposure conditions for each participant. Results showed significant main effects of exposure and Noise+HAV exposure led to the greatest change in OAEs. The current prospective study in the laboratory environment was planned to study the combined effects of noise and vibration on inner ear auditory functioning.

METHODS

Participants

The research received approval from the Institutional Review Board at the authors' academic institution. The study enrolled twenty graduate students in good health, comprising thirteen males and seven females. These participants had no previous exposure to occupational noise or HAV. All participants were required to show normal middle ear function, characterized by: a) Jerger type A tympanograms, b) normal ear canal volume (1.0 – 2.0 cc) and c) normal static compliance (ranging between 0.3-1.6 cc). Upon their arrival, the participants were provided with information about the testing procedures and subsequently signed informed consent forms. BMI measurements were completed for all participants to account for individual and gender-related differences that can impact vibration transfer for HAV to the head. Table 1 shows demographic characteristics for male and female participants included in the current study.

Table 1: Descriptive data with mean (range) and standard deviation for participants.

	Males	Females
Age (yrs)	Mean = 28.5 (20-33) SD = 3.9	Mean = 29.6 (23-38) SD = 5.4
Body Mass Index	Mean = 27.6 (17.9-39) SD = 5.4	Mean = 24.9 (18.3-31.2) SD = 3.8
Right Ear Volume(cc)	Mean = 1.5 (.7-2.1) SD = 0.4	Mean = 1.2 (.7-1.7) SD = 0.4
Static Compliance	Mean=0.71 (0.5-1.6) SD = 0.30	Mean=1.2 (0.7-1.7) SD = 0.20
Noise Dose (dBA)	Mean = 81.9 (76.5-85.5) SD = 2.6	Mean = 83.1 (80-85.8) SD = 2.1
Vibration Transfer to Head (m/sec²)	Mean = 0.08 (0.0-0.3) SD = 0.09	Mean = 0.07 (0-0.20) SD = 0.08

Noise + Vibration Box

A custom-made wooden box was made to house the Craftsman Drill at torque setting of 9 to generate vibration (Hand Arm Vibration or HAV) and noise. The box was put over a table with an option of adjustable height (See Figure 2). The height of the table was adjusted depending on the height of the subject so that the elbow is at 90° during Noise + Hand Arm Vibration exposure. Typically, the box produced noise close to 82.5 dB and vibration 0.57m/sec². These exposures are below the hazardous levels reported by OSHA and are thus associated with minimal risk to hearing and hand functioning. During the Hand Arm Vibration + Noise exposure, the subject was asked to put his/her actual hand gently over the vibration box with 500 grams force (sandbag) on the marked hand. During noise exposure condition, a gloved hand was put over the vibration wooden box to substitute subject's hand. The latex gloves were filled with sand equivalent to the weight using segment weight as percentage of body weight guide. Then 500 grams sandbag was placed over the subject's hand which acted as a constant same force for all the subjects. The sand filled glove hand equivalent to the weight of the hand of the subject was used to maintain consistency during noise exposure with the subject standing behind the box with no actual vibration transferring through the body. A cross mark was made on the wall right in front of the eyes of the subject and they were instructed to keep their body still and look at the mark during Noise + HAV to avoid the movement of head/body that could add to the vibration in the accelerometers.

The personal noise exposure was recorded with Larson Davis Spark 706 noise dosimeter. The hand arm vibration was measured with Xsens Dot at a sampling frequency of 120 Hz, tied with Velcro on wrist, above elbow and above the right ear on head. Accelerometer vibration data via bluetooth were recorded on the phone and later transferred in Microsoft Excel files for data processing.

FIGURE 1: Equipment used for noise and vibration exposures

Audiometric Testing

Pure tone audiometric testing was administered within a professional sound booth using a GSI 61 Clinical Audiometer. This evaluation covered frequencies of 500 Hz, 1000 Hz, 2000 Hz, 3000 Hz, and 4000 Hz. Following this, the ear canal volume (needed to account for individual and gender-related ear differences across participants) and static compliance (to confirm normal eardrum mobility) were measured for the right ear of each participant using a GSI Tymstar middle ear analyzer. The right ear was selected for the ear canal volume measurement all participants were right-handed.

OAE Testing

Transient evoked otoacoustic emissions (TEOAEs) were captured utilizing the Scout Sport Bio-logic System Corporation equipment. Using a probe that delivers broad band clicks, cochlear responses can be obtained by a miniature microphone located in the ear canal. A pre-exposure TEOAE was recorded first in all participants. Subsequently, each participant was subjected to two different types of exposures, randomly assigned as follows: a) Noise, and b) Noise + Hand Arm Vibration (Figure 4), each exposure lasting for two minutes. Following the first exposure condition, a post-exposure TEOAE was recorded in the same participant. Then each participant was given a five-minutes rest period with no noise or hand-arm vibration exposure. Following the second exposure condition, TEOAEs were recorded again for the third time. TEOAE SNR was measured at each of the frequencies (1 kHz, 1.5 kHz, 2 kHz, 3 kHz, 4 kHz) by subtracting the noise floor (dB) from the amplitude of the OAE (dB) recorded from the probe microphones. Figure 2 shows the workflow used in the study. To account for possible order effects, the order of conditions (Noise versus Noise+Vibration) were counterbalanced across participants.

FIGURE 2: Workflow for OAE measurements.

RESULTS

Statistical analysis was conducted using IBM SPSS version 27 (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences). The primary independent variable under investigation was the exposure conditions, categorized into two groups: Noise and Noise+HAV, which were assessed across two levels of repeated measures factors, namely Pre-Exposure SNR and Post-Exposure SNR. A linear regression model used.

Effect of gender

Male and female participants showed equivalence and there were no statistically significant effects across gender for: a) ear canal volume ($F=0.34$; $p=0.55$); b) hearing sensitivity ($F=0.01$; $p=0.90$); and c) BMI ($F=0.85$; $p=0.35$). Figure 3 shows similar averages for hand arm vibration in male and female participants when measured different locations (from the box to head via wrist and elbow). As illustrated below, the vibration is highest in the box and significantly declines as it reaches the head.

FIGURE 3: Vibration accelerometry results from multiple sensor locations.

Change in OAEs following exposures

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) results shown below in Table 2 indicate significant ($p<0.05$) main effects of time and interaction effects of gender x exposure x time. To control potential confounding variables, the following covariates were incorporated into the statistical analysis: ear canal volume, BMI (Body Mass Index), and hearing sensitivity. The effects of each of these individual covariates were not found to be statistically significant for: a) ear canal volume ($F=0.34$; $p=0.55$); b) hearing sensitivity ($F=0.01$; $p=0.90$); and c) BMI ($F=0.85$; $p=0.35$).

Table 2: Analysis of Variance results for OAE SNR

Source	Sum of Squares	dF	Mean Squares	F-ratio	Probability of significance
Time (Pre-Exposure SNR versus Post-Exposure SNR)	14.52	1	14.52	5.10	0.025**
Exposure (Noise versus Noise+HAV)	2.17	1	2.17	.108	0.742
Gender	26.54	1	26.54	1.32	0.251
Exposure*Time	5.72	11	5.72	2.00	0.16
Time*Gender	19.97	1	19.97	7.014	.009
Exposure*Gender	4.17	1	4.17	.20	.655
Exposure*Time*Gender	14.24	1	14.24	5.00	.026**
Error	546.49	192	2.84		

For post-hoc pairwise comparison of means, Fisher's least significant difference (LSD) was used. No significant differences between means for the condition (Noise+HAV versus Noise) were found. Fisher's least significant difference (LSD) for pairwise comparison of means showed significant differences between pre-exposure and post-exposure SNR in female participants in the HAV + Noise condition (illustrated in Figure 4 below).

FIGURE 4: OAE SNR by gender and condition.

The relationship between Pre-Exposure SNR and Post-Exposure SNR for participants is shown in Fig. 5 below. The R value of 0.75 supports a moderate positive association between pre-exposure and post-exposure SNR. This correlation R value may be skewed due to higher OAE SNRs found in female participants.

Figure 5

FIGURE 5: Correlation between pre-exposure and post-exposure OAE SNR

DISCUSSION

Current study results indicate that adding HAV to noise significantly increased OAE SNR in female participants. While this may look like an improvement in OAEs in females, it can actually put females at greater risk for noise-vibration interactions. Increased excitation in OHC electromotility (increased SNR) over long periods of time from over exposure to noise and vibration can increase the risk of injury to the inner ear. The following synergistic interactions and underlying mechanisms will be used to explain the current findings.

5.1 Synergistic interaction of noise and low frequency vibration

Results of our study support previous studies supporting synergistic effects of noise and vibration on the auditory system in humans. The interaction between hand-arm vibration (HAV) and noise on hearing was studied by Pyykko et al. [11]. Pyykko et al. [11] suggested that vibration triggered a reduction in blood flow to the cochlea due to activation of the sympathetic nervous system, leading to an increased risk of hearing loss. Pettersson et al. [12] studied the combined effect of noise and hand vibration on temporary threshold shift (TTS). The three exposure conditions were (1) noise alone, (2) HAV alone and (3) noise + HAV combined. The HAV exposure involved gripping with a force of $10(\pm 5)$ N on a gripping handle. Each condition lasted for 20 minutes with a rest period of 24 hours. Results indicated that TTS effects were the greatest for the combined noise + HAV exposure reflecting the risk of vibration as an additional auditory hazard when combined with noise. Sisto et al. [2] used 3 exposure conditions for a duration of 3 minutes each followed by a rest period of 4 minutes. The conditions used were; HAV only, noise only, and Noise+HAV. The subjects in Sisto study were exposed to a HAV dose of 30m/sec^2 at 60Hz and using 20% of the Maximum Voluntary Contraction (MVC) by gripping the handle connected to a shaker. The noise dose exposure was white noise at 94 dBA. DPOAEs were measured before and after each of the exposure conditions for each participant. Results of the Sisto et al. (2017) study showed that significant main effects of exposure and Noise+HAV exposure led to the greatest change in OAEs.

5.2 Possible mechanisms underlying interaction of noise and vibration

Based on a piezoelectric model by Ramamoorthy, Deo, & Grosh [1] the outer hair cells (OHCs) provides both forward transduction of energy (mechanical deflection of OHCs stereocilia to electrical energy in the form of action potential), along with a reverse transduction (electrical currents from OHCs feeding mechanical energy to the inner hair cells -IHCs). These properties make the OHCs function as an active bio-amplifier located within the cochlea. When loud noise exposures or other occupational hazards diminish OHCs function, thus amplifier action is lost resulting in irreversible Sensorineural Hearing Loss (SNHL).

Noise exposures tend to have mechanical effects on hair cells in the Organ of Corti. Specifically, OHCs are designed to be highly sensitive to soft sounds and enhance sensitivity of the cochlea in fine tuning of the cochlea for frequency resolution. Due to their positioning and attachment to the gelatinous tectorial membrane in which they are embedded, OHCs are subjected to severe shearing forces due to mechanical effects of noise on OHCs. Excessive shearing forces has a negative effect on the stereocilia of the hair cells in the basilar membrane of the cochlea, which can cause cell death.

We speculate that when HAV is added to loud noise, electromotility of OHC may be enhanced due to three possible operations: 1) increased activity of OHC stereocilia that are directly coupled to the tectorial membrane, 2) increased motion of the basilar membrane that displaces the entire Organ of Corti in a linear fashion, and 3) increased blood flow to the cochlea.

Conclusions

In the current study, changes in OAEs were assessed before and after exposure to: 1) noise and 2) noise+HAV. The simultaneous exposure to Noise + HAV resulted in an increased OAE SNR in female participants compared to males. . Based on our study results, the Noise+HAV condition increased OAE SNR in female participants putting them at greater risk. Increased OHC electromotility (increased SNR) over long periods of time from over exposure to noise and vibration can increase the risk of injury to the inner ear.

The current has several limitations: 1) small sample size, 2) only younger participants with excellent hearing were included, 3) relatively lower noise and vibration exposures were used when compared with those typically experienced by individuals in occupations that face Noise+HAV exposures (miners, oil rig workers, forestry workers, machinists) used and 4) only right handed participants were included.

Comments addressed from MOH workshop reviewers

[Ernst Dalhoff]

Figure 1 caption: I would recommend to call it workflow, not setup. But you should add that the sequence was randomized, as the figure suggests it would always start with noise + HAW

Corrected, thanks.

For Figures, it would be nice to have a caption!

Done

Figure 8 shows more than 100 points. Am I right to guess that this is due to having a point for $n = n_freqbands * n_subj$? I would recommend to make that clear in the caption and/or in the methods/discussion section.

If this assumption is correct, the figure suggests that the statistical effect is driven by 9 points which could be from 2..9 subjects (which probably all were female). I think we would like to know, how many subjects led to the points below $RD = -5.0$ dB, could be in the caption, but should probably also be added in the discussion.

Added to discussion, thanks for comment.

[Pim Van Dijk]

On page 4: you write "two levels of vibration exposure (5Hz and 10Hz)." Is suppose you mean: two expore frequencies (not levels).

Corrected

Figures: Is it possible to add a measure of variability (for example, standard deviation)?

Completed, thanks.

Figures 5-8: add figure captions. Add units, where applicable. That is, SNR is in dB, I presume.

Completed thanks.

Vibration exposure resulted in increase SNR in females. This could be stated clearer in the Conclusion. What puzzles me is that vibration actually improved OAEs.

Discussed in conclusions, thanks.

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